

The Power within: Exploring the Link between Psychological Capital and Academic Performance amongst Adolescents

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Referred to as a positive state of mind, psychological capital encompasses hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism. Considering the impact, a positive state of mind can have on achievement, the current research attempted to explore the association of psychological capital on academic performance. For this purpose, a sample of 400 students (13 to 18 years old) was selected from different schools in Panjab. Academic psychological capital Scale (Luthans et al., 2012) and Grade Point Average (GPA) were used to study the relationship between adolescent psychological capital and their academic performance. Mean, SD, correlation and linear regression analysis were performed utilizing SPSS Software 26. Correlation Analysis found that all four components of PsyCap, i.e., hope, self-efficacy, resilience and optimism as individual constructs and psychological capital as whole were significantly and positively related with academic performance. In addition, regression analysis revealed that PsyCap positively and significantly predicted Academic performance in adolescents.

Keywords: Psychological capital, adolescents, academic performance

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescence is a critical developmental phase, marking the transition from childhood to adulthood, encompassing individuals aged 10 to 19 years. (Maaan et al., 2021; Veleshala et al., 2019). While undergoing this transition, adolescents face numerous developmental changes, like physical, cognitive, emotional and social (Fuhrmann, 2017; Izzani et al., 2024; Galván & Tottenham, 2016). Adolescents feel there is a lot to adjust to and adapt to, which eventually starts to negatively impact their academic performance (Gicharu & Sindabi, n.d.). At this crucial point in their lives, having a resource in the form of positive strength would facilitate one's adjustment capability to deal with the ongoing developmental changes. Herein, PsyCap plays a wonderful role by bringing in a positive state of mind and has been associated with enhancing academic performance, enriching interpersonal relationships, increasing Well-being and reducing stress among students (Chen & Weng, 2022; Bhagat & Kaur, 2025).

PsyCap, or positive psychological capital, is envisioned as a higher-order construct consisting of 4 positive mental health states, namely, Hope, Self-efficacy, Resilience, and Optimism (HERO) (Luthans et al., 2007). It is a state-like construct (Luthans et al., 2008) which can be further enhanced with various positive intervention techniques (Luthans et al., 2014). Psychological capital is a construct lying beyond traditional economic capital (i.e., what a person

acquires, his assets, & resources), social capital (all individual close relations, peer groups, & networks), and knowledge capital (what an individual knows, his knowledge, skills, & talent) as suggested by Luthans et al. (2004).

Components of Psychological Capital

- *Hope* is defined as a positive motivational mindset comprising the interaction of two components, i.e., agency and pathways, where agency refers to one's motivation to accomplish a set task and pathways correspond to the methods or ways through which a particular task would be achieved (Snyder, 2002; Luthans et al., 2008).
- *Self-efficacy* pertains to one's confidence in one's ability or in other words, an individual's perceived capacity to accomplish specific behavior (Ozkalp, 2009; Bandura, 1997).
- *Optimism* is the attribution style in which an optimistic person attributes good events to internal, stable, and global causes, and perceives bad events as caused by external, unstable, and specific factors (Seligman, 1998).
- *Resilience* denotes one's capability to rebound from setbacks, apprehension, risk, debacle, elevated responsibilities, and successfully adapt to ongoing changing and stressful demands of life (Masten & Reed, 2002; Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004).

A foundational research on this area was conducted by Luthans et al. (2012) who found that PsyCap positively predicted the academic performance of a selected sample of 95 undergraduates. In line with this, Carmona-Halty et al. (2019) attempted to explore the interplay of psychological capital with academic performance amongst 407 adolescents (12-18 years old). The study results portrayed a direct positive association of psychological capital with academic performance.

However, other researchers such as Veldsman et al. (2018) reported that only hope and self-efficacy are positively linked with academic performance, although overall PsyCap showed a positive correlation with academic performance. Similarly, Onivehu (2020)

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reported self-efficacy to be negatively related to academic performance. Although, this study also reported that psychological capital as a whole construct is positively linked with academic performance.

Academic performance among adolescents is influenced by cognitive as well as other crucial psychological factors. Positive strengths like psychological capital and its subcomponents-including hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism-are well-established constructs in facilitating employee performance, well-being, and overall job satisfaction (Cetin, 2011; Tripathi, 2011; Youssef-Morgan & Luthans, 2015) in organizational fields among adults. A few studies in the academic area revealed that psychological capital aids in promoting well-being, improving performance, enhancing academic engagement, and buffering stress among students (Bhagat & Kaur, 2025; Riolli et al., 2012). However, this beneficial impact of psychological capital needs further exploration, as published studies in the educational field are scarce, and this domain remains largely unexplored, particularly among adolescents. Hence, the current research attempts to bridge the gap in existing literature by exploring the salient role of psychological capital in enhancing adolescents' academic performance. Moreover, there is a notable gap in studies probing this variable in the Indian context. Given its potential benefits for adolescents' mental health, Psychological Capital deserves further exploration alongside its key correlates. In addition, insights from this study may be beneficial for designing interventions needed to expand one's Psychological Capital, thereby bolstering students' inner strength to handle and deal with developmental challenges during adolescence.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the relationship of psychological capital and its sub-components, viz., hope, self-efficacy, resilience and optimism with academic performance.
- To study the role of psychological capital in predicting academic performance.

Hypotheses of the Study

On the basis of above review, the following hypotheses are framed:

- Psychological Capital and all its subcomponents, viz., Hope, Self-efficacy, Optimism and Resilience are expected to be positively related to Academic Performance.
- Psychological capital is expected to significantly predict academic performance.

Method

Participants

A total sample of 400 adolescents (200 Male & 200 female) studying in Grades 9 to 12 and belonging to middle socio-economic status was selected for this study. All selected adolescents fell within the age range of 13 to 18 years and were chosen from several schools located in the Punjab region using a simple random sampling technique.

Measures

Academic Psychological Capital: Luthans (2012) designed a scale for the student population to assess their level of psychological capital within the school environment. It consists of a total of 24 statements, with 6 statements measuring each facet: hope, self-

efficacy, resilience, and optimism. The reported Cronbach's alpha for the PsyCap is 0.89, and for its subdimensions i.e., hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism subscales it is 0.76, 0.84, 0.71, and 0.79, respectively (Luthans & Avolio, 2007).

Academic Performance: For assessing the adolescents' Academic Performance, their previous two semester' scores were obtained in the form of Grade Point Average (GPA) collected through their class teacher.

Statistical Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were computed, along with Pearson correlation, and linear regression was performed on the data and subsequently analyzed using SPSS 26 software.

Procedure

The study aimed to explore the impact of psychological capital and its four major constructs on students' academic performance. Permission was obtained from the school principal and the participating adolescents. Participants were given all necessary instructions verbally and were informed about the aims and objectives of the research. Their consent was obtained and a set of questionnaires, including psychological capital scale and demographic information, was distributed to the adolescents during the zero-hour period at school. Participants were clearly informed about the confidentiality of their responses-that is, their responses would be used solely for research purposes.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Mean, SD for Study Variable

Variable	M	SD
1 Psychological Capital	103.92	14.218
2 Hope	27.20	5.291
3 Self- efficacy	26.80	5.347
4 Resilience	24.91	4.540
5 Optimism	25.02	3.918
6 Academic Performance	71.61%	12.61%

Table 2 shows that hope ($r = .188, p < .01$), self-efficacy ($r = .170, p < .01$), resilience ($r = .145, p < .01$), and optimism ($r = .195, p < .01$) were all significantly and positively correlated with academic performance. Moreover, psychological capital as a whole was also found to be significantly and positively correlated with academic performance ($r = .234, p < .01$).

Table 3 shows the impact of psychological capital on academic performance in adolescents. The results ($R^2 = 0.055; F(1, 398) = 23.04, p < .001$) indicate that the predictor variable, psychological capital, explains 5.5% of the variance in the outcome variable (academic performance). The beta value of 0.21 suggests that with every one-unit increase in psychological capital, academic performance increases by 0.21 units. These findings reveal that psychological capital positively and significantly predicts academic performance, although the effect is modest.

Thus, the hypotheses have been supported by results. Obtained similar finding were reported by Sheikhi and Shahmorady (2016) who explored the association between psychological capital and academic performance among 207 students and observed that all four sub-components of PsyCap, i.e., hope, self-efficacy, resilience,

Table 2*Pearson Correlation between Psychological Capital, its Dimensions, and Academic Performance*

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 Psychological Capital	1					
2 Hope	.834**	1				
3 Self- efficacy	.806**	.625**	1			
4 Resilience	.677**	.419**	.327**	1		
5 Optimism	.619**	.337**	.337**	.286**	1	
6 Academic Performance	.234**	.188**	.170**	.145**	.195**	1

Note. **. Value of Correlation significant at the 0.01 level. *. Value of Correlation significant at the 0.05 level

Table 3*Linear Regression of Association between Psychological Capital and Academic Performance (N=400)*

Predictor	B	SE B	β	t	p
Psychological Capital	0.21	0.04	0.23	4.80**	< .001

Note. $R^2 = 0.055$; $F(1, 398) = 23.04$, $p < .001$, $**p < .001$

and optimism, were significantly and positively related to academic performance, as well as regression analysis revealing psychological capital acts as a predictor for academic performance. Moreover, it was found that overall psychological capital as a unified construct is a more robust predictor of academic performance than any of its individual components. Similarly, Martinez et al. (2019) attempted to examine psychological capital and its components, i.e., self-efficacy, hope, resilience, and optimism, as predictors of academic performance. The results showed a positive relationship between PsyCap and academic performance, which further concludes that personal resources like psychological capital are important predictors of academic performance in students. Moreover, the study results reported that psychological capital serves as a predictor of academic performance. Khan et al. (2022) identified existence of a positive and significant relationship between one's psychological capital and their scores in academics in a cohort of 450 students and also found that psychological capital significantly predicted academic performance. Kutz (2020) delves into the connection between academic psychological capital and academic performance (measured in terms of GPA) on a sample of 547 students. These recruited students were evaluated with the Academic Psychological Capital Scale by Luthans (2012) and their academic performance was measured in terms of their GPA. The study demonstrates a modest yet statistically significant positive link of academic PsyCap with GPA ($r = .190$, $p < .01$). Furthermore, regression analysis reveals that PsyCap contributes to approximately 3.6% of the variability in GPA.

Conclusion and Implications of the Study

The current research reflects crucial findings by exploring the interplay of psychological capital with academic performance. Findings revealed that psychological capital as a whole enhances one's level of academic performance. Sub- constructs of psychological capital, i.e., hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism, as individual resources were found to be positively linked

with academic performance. In addition, results showed that psychological capital serves as a predictor for academic performance, although the reported effect was modest. These results further conclude that accumulation of positive resources such as self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience would boost emotional strength in adolescents, eventually leading to enhancement in their academic performance. Importantly, psychological capital is considered a state-like construct-meaning it can be further developed through positive intervention techniques (Luthans et al., 2014; Meyers et al., 2015). Various Stakeholders need to understand the impact of psychological capital and implement various positive intervention techniques needed to develop psychological capital in their institution. Enhanced level of psychological capital can not only enrich academic performance, but also bolster one's self-esteem, which eventually results in overall growth and development in adolescents (Schonfeld & Hess, 2024).

Suggestions and Limitations of the Study

The current study reveals a modest predictive effect of psychological capital on academic performance, suggesting the presence of other independent variables, such as academic engagement and study habits, that also contribute to academic success. Thus, future research should explore additional predictors of academic performance. In addition, future studies should adopt a longitudinal research design to further investigate how psychological capital influences academic outcomes over time.

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